

Supplementary information

Towards a Valorization of Corn Bioethanol Side Streams: Chemical Characterization of Post Fermentation Corn Oil and Thin Stillage

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Figure S1. Scheme of grain to ethanol process and its connection to the EXCornsEED project.

Table S1. Sampling date at ENVIRAL's plants of the different side stream lots analysed in the study.

SAMPLING DATE		
LOT	CORN OIL	THIN STILLAGE
1	29/6/2018	29/6/2018
2	22/10/2018	22/10/2018
3	26/11/2018	26/11/2018
4	9/12/2018	5/12/2018
5	18/1/2019	18/1/2019
6	25/2/2019	25/2/2019
7	22/4/2019	18/4/2019
8	23/5/2019	24/5/2019
9	21/6/2019	21/6/2019